

Bristlebots – are they alive? Epistemic insight workshops using small things to ask big questions

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Abstract A small, handmade and inexpensive robot can help students across a range of ages unpack and explore big questions around the nature of life, curiosity and creativity. Via a series of workshops students learn how to frame and investigate different types of questions including big questions that bridge science, computing and the wider humanities.

The Bristlebot

This article explains an introductory workshop and a sequence of follow-up workshops for students ranging from key stage 2 to key stage 4 (ages 7–16) that build ideas and interest about the nature of life, curiosity and creativity using a Bristlebot robot.

A Bristlebot is a simple robot created from a toothbrush head (Figure 1). To make one, cut away the handle of a toothbrush and just leave the head and bristles. Then attach either a miniature vibrating motor or the type of buzzer that makes mobile phones vibrate. The Bristlebot is powered by a small, single-cell battery, the type you might find in a digital clock. The vibrations

Figure 1 The Bristlebot

act through the bristles to give the robot motion. Prior to the work described in this article, most examples of the use of these robots have focused mainly on the design and technology side in schools, although some research around collective behaviour and the swarming of organisms has been conducted using them (Giomi, Hawley-Weld and Mahadevan, 2013).

Tips for building the bot

To build the Bristlebot you will need to ensure that you have a suitable toothbrush with flat bristles and a flat surface on the toothbrush head upon which to locate the buzzer and single-cell battery. The cheapest toothbrushes were found to provide the best results. The buzzers we used were sourced online from Amazon and we have found so far that the most reliable are 1.5V/0.05A 10×2.7 mm Coin Mobile Phone Vibration Motors by Uxcell. These buzzers come with suitably long connecting wires. Standard LR44 or AG13 alkaline cell batteries are used as the main power source. It is worth buying long-shelf-life batteries in case you need to store these devices for any length of time.

Some investigation was carried out into how to fix the battery and buzzer to the toothbrush – eventually it was found that small, 12×12×2 mm double-sided adhesive foam pads (as used in greeting-card making) were the most reliable and easiest to use in building the Bristlebots. The only other challenge was to strip away enough bare wire from the insulated leads to the buzzer to make a suitable connection. The wires on the buzzer are very thin so this takes some care and is something that may best be carried out by an adult with appropriate tools, such as a wire-stripping tool. You have to decide whether a key objective is the construction of the Bristlebots, or simply their use. If it is the latter, partially constructed Bristlebots will save considerable time.

Once the Bristlebot is constructed it will move around a flat surface with some ease. It won't cross any irregular surfaces, however. A disposable plastic dinner plate or a small serving tray provides a good way to enclose the Bristlebots and to stop them escaping over the edges of the tables (Figure 2). It also provides a bounded environment for the students to watch multiple Bristlebots interact.

The Bristlebot workshops

The Bristlebots in the epistemic insight workshops were used to encourage a range of primary and secondary students to examine a number of big questions. In this article I describe three of the basic workshops, beginning with the introductory workshop. More have been designed and others are under development.

The initial 'Is it alive?' workshop

Is it alive? This was the initial question posed to all the groups about the Bristlebot as it scurried around its bounded environment. This was followed up by a review and retrieval of knowledge and ideas around what we mean by alive, both in a scientific sense as well as in everyday use of the word alive. So not just whether something is alive or not, but what does it mean to be alive? Here we invited the students to consider what subject disciplines could help us to understand this and why life matters to us. It was an opportunity to remind students about the difference between the use of scientific language and other forms of more emotive and qualitative language. This was then linked to the scientific characteristics of life and the often-used acronym MRS GREN (movement, respiration, sensitivity, growth, reproduction, excretion and nutrition). The recall and use of these characteristics allowed a dialogic space (Alexander, 2017) to be created that enabled the students to discuss each of the terms and how, for example with growth, some things may appear to be alive and indeed, may grow, but are not counted as alive. One example of this raised by the students was that of a volcano as it grows and moves and may appear in a number of ways to be alive, but is not. This in turn allowed the students to reflect upon the Bristlebot, to pick the characteristics of life it appeared to have, and to reevaluate whether the Bristlebot was or was not alive in a scientific sense.

The students were then asked to consider what aspects they would change about their Bristlebot, what they might add, to make it more alive. The response to this followed very much along key stage lines, with the primary key stage 2 (ages 7–11) students proposing adding senses such as sight or touch, whereas the key stage 3 (ages 11–14) students went further, looking at

Figure 2 Bristlebots on a plate

a means to process information, a brain, as well as one student proposing that the Bristlebot be given 'a sense of purpose'.

This in turn led to a discussion around cultural references to robots and artificial intelligence (AI) in stories and films. It was noted that the most common reference for the students was to *The Terminator* and *The Matrix* films, whereas even science fiction from 15 years ago, such as the Replicators from the popular *Stargate* film series or Isaac Asimov's robot stories and his Three Laws of Robotics, were not known by the students. Going back to earlier robots in science fiction, it was clear that the students had not encountered Robby the Robot who appeared both in the classic film *Forbidden Planet* and in the long-running 1960s TV series *Lost in Space*.

The session for primary students was then finished with a review of the AI in the students' lives (such as *Alexa*, *Cortana* and *Google*) and how this was viewed as both a promise for the future as well as a challenge. This discussion was initiated by interacting with the Bristlebots and was followed by activities that produced a range of stepping-off points, where the discussion could have taken off into other directions or into other investigations. Examples are: What is artificial intelligence? How could we test whether an artefact has intelligence and know that it is being used to influence or determine the behaviour of a robot?

The 'Can it have a sense of curiosity?' workshop

The secondary key stage 3 students were presented with a shortened version of the 'Is it alive?' workshop and then they were asked to consider whether the Bristlebot or a development of it could have its own sense of curiosity. This prompted a discussion around what we mean by curiosity as well as the things that help us to be curious about the world across a range of subjects.

This in turn led to investigation about how we might get these things and build them into our robots as well as what it is that drives this sense of curiosity. A question posed to the students to support this thinking, was: 'Is

NASA's Mars rover *Curiosity* really curious or is it just doing what it's told to do by its operator back on Earth? The students were then invited to review their thinking about curiosity across a range of subject domains, and were invited to use the Epistemic Insight Discipline Wheel to unpick the range of subject areas that they had been considering and why (Figure 3). This session was concluded by reviewing ideas about how we could stimulate our own sense of curiosity.

The 'Can it be creative?' workshop

A third workshop, aimed at older secondary key stage 3 students and higher, was a development out of the previous workshop on curiosity, with the main question: 'Can a robot really be creative?' This workshop, as with the previous one, started off with a shortened version of the 'Is it alive?' workshop. This was then followed by asking the students to consider whether a robot could make a good friend and what attributes a good friend might have. This conversation was then steered towards one specific trait, tastes in music, and whether our friends might like the same music as us; and, if we were to build a robot companion, what taste in music would it have? Would it just be mimicking our choices or could a robot have the ability to be creative and not only choose its own music but make its own music? A special Bristlebot connected to a computer that created music via a small *Scratch* program was demonstrated to the students to show how random music could be generated. The question being asked here was: 'Do robots only carry out the things that they are programmed to do or can they go beyond their programming?' This led the students to thinking about how much freedom to create we have in reality, and to a discussion around different forms of creativity, such as the Four C Model of Creativity (Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009).

Conclusions

Overall, the Bristlebots have shown that small simple devices can assist students, across a range of ages, to start to unpack big questions. This was demonstrated

Figure 3 The 'Discipline Wheel'

across these workshops with a diverse range of students from very different schools, all actively engaged in developing their ideas and challenging each other to think beyond single-subject domains in order to review their big questions.

As part of this, we used a range of pedagogical tools and objectives drawn from the Epistemic Insight Framework, such as the 'Discipline Wheel' (Billingsley, 2017; Billingsley, Abedin and Nassaji, 2020), to assist the students in these workshops to become more epistemically insightful in looking at ways of knowing and how they interact across multidisciplinary arenas. This was demonstrated by the students' range of ideas and their willingness to be part of a dialogic space.

References

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